

FACTORS AFFECTING THE CAREER DECISION-MAKING OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN SRI-LANKA.

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Abstract : The study is conducted to analyze the factors which are affecting the Career Decision-Making of Secondary School Students in Sri Lanka. Three factors have been explained in this study which affect a student's career decision making as follow, parent's impact, educational impact and basic needs impact on a secondary school student. The study was conducted on a random sample of employees from various industries. The population of this study is 100 workers including 65 males and 35 females in western province. This study used interview method as primary data and journals, research papers, articles and books were used as secondary data. As a result of discussions with the study's population, it is possible to conclude that parents play an important role, with the majority having a negative impact on their children's professional development. It also emphasizes the significance of teachers' participation in decision-making. Another factor which impacts career decision-making is socioeconomic circumstances. Also, students' dropout percentage is increasing due to lack of basic needs. This study suggests, it necessitates methods that go beyond traditional procedures, as well as a team approach with kids, parents, teachers, administrators, community-based groups, businesses, and the government working together to achieve a single national objective. Also, parents should be concerned about their children's motivation and enthusiasm in pursuing a vocation.

Keywords – *Career Decision-making Difficulties, Career choice, Family influence, Basic needs*

INTRODUCTION

Secondary school is the first step in a student's life toward deciding on a career path. This decision generally requires extensive study and knowledge of the numerous options available. Since students' lack of maturity at this age, they need continuous encouragement, interaction, and guidance in order to make better career decisions. It is critical to provide students with an accepting and transparent environment, so that they can learn about and understand different fields before making any decisions (Akpochafo, 2020, p. 5920). While guidance is necessary at every stage and in every sphere of human life, it is especially important at secondary school level due to the sensitivity of students' ages at this level, which is particularly valuable from an educational standpoint as well as in terms of growth, and a detailed study of the need for guidance at secondary school level for better progress and personality development (이희인 & Hyunchul Kim, 2015, p. 179).

This paper explains the 'Factors Affecting the Career Decision - Making of Secondary School Students in Sri Lanka'. There are three factors have been explained in the study which affect a student's career decision making as follow, parent's impact, educational impact and basic needs impact on a secondary school student. Other than students' own wishes and preferences, powerful influencing factors play a role in career choice. While family is heavily influenced by the general public, personal interests are formed by one's family, especially their parents, and the environment. The degree to which the general public and family affect students' career choices varies based on how the students were raised and how responsive they are to social changes (Swinhoe, 1967, p. 149).

The second factor explains regarding how education impact on decision of choosing career of students. The students were overwhelmingly encouraged to attend school by their parents, but some parents were unable to provide career advice due to a lack of knowledge about various occupations. Therefore, teachers in schools may have served as career counselors, but they seemed to be unsure of how to guide students into their ideal potential occupations. There are no institutional arrangements in place to provide career counseling to students. As a result, educational and career counseling has become critical for students who are deciding what area of study to pursue for their potential careers. It makes difficulty to decide a student's career (Parent's Role in Career Selection, 2017).

Apart from that, the study also explains how basic needs impact on children's education and mandatory needs such as foods, clothes and shelter requirements to continue their studies. Without fulfilling these needs' children cannot focus on their studies and it may affect the personality of the students. It leads them to dropout from the school and seek a job to fire out the hunger and as well as due to several reason decision has been taken by students (Lumen Learning, 2020). As a result, above factors influence secondary school career decisions, and the study focuses on them, as such, Parent's impact, educational system impact and basic needs impact.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is identifying the factors which are affecting the student's career decision making. It also aims to suggest an environment of transparency and acceptance to reduce wrong decisions by students. Furthermore, it educates and aware of common problems and situations that occur to students. It is for those who are constantly involved with them.

METHODOLOGY

The population of the research was, 100 workers who works in bazaar, grocery shops, garments, I.T sectors and some other B.P.O sectors, and they were about 18 to 20 years old, both male and female. We conducted interview as primary data and secondary data has been collected from magazines, journal articles, books and paper articles as secondary data.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The effect of a person's career choice is long-lasting. It serves as an indicator and determinant of their future level of income, nature of employment, and, as a result, has an effect on an individual's personality, demeanor, and outlook. As a result, one bad decision will alter a person's destiny. It is difficult for anyone to make a career decision. This individual activity is reflected in a nation's economic growth on a larger scale. Individuals that are misfits at work are less creative and effective, and as a result, they are unable to achieve their objectives (Kazi & Akhlaq, 2017).

FACTORS AFFECTING THE CAREER DECISION-MAKING

Parents impact on choosing career path

We all recognize the value of learning, but many parents question whether pushing their children to their own ideas as their child's career and study is a good idea. But there are many consequences which explain why it's not a good view point. From a psychological perspective, the more holistic view of parental impact on the child's career growth is favored as children begin to transition into adulthood through the creation of their own identity, as it takes into account the entire background of the adolescent's decision-making. Parenting is not a one-way street; rather, it is part of a broader multilayered structure of everyday life. Furthermore, while parents are commonly considered to be optimistic influences on their children's career decisions, it is also possible that parents are negatively influencing their children's vocational growth (Clutter, 2010).

The pressure to succeed in school or encouragement for only a limited number of occupations may restrict an adolescent's ability to pursue alternative careers that are better suited to him or her. For example, if parents state that they will only pay for college if their child pursues certain majors, if they overtly tell the child that he or she is expected to graduate with a specific degree and work for a bank or law firm, or if they subtly reinforce the value of some jobs while discounting others, these are all examples of how parents may negatively narrow their children's career options. Through injecting their own prejudices and attitudes into specific occupational fields, parents' financial interests and aspirations play a role in their direct or indirect impact on their children's career choice. When it comes to career preparation, what parents do and how they behave have a much greater impact on their children than what they say. Furthermore, the young adult's perception of his or her parents' expectations can affect their own career preferences, depending on whether the teenager feels obligated to embrace or reject their parents' perspectives (Kazi & Akhlaq, 2017, p. 193).

Parents recognize the value of their children studying and getting a good academic education in order for them to become effective professionals. However, as a result of this, they often put unrealistic demands on their children and make emotional mistakes. It's all too normal to feel compelled to push children to be smarter. Parents may enroll their children in co-curricular activities including music, singing, athletics, drawing, and other classes. Children, on the other hand, may dislike certain activities, leaving them upset and leading to a variety of physical, emotional, and psychological consequences. If parents continually press their children to engage in academic events, the child may lose interest in going to school. They may also lose their routine,

such as eating and sleeping schedules, which may become unbalanced. Because of parental control, children may be less interested in completing their homework. Due to the fact that their relationships with friends and classmates become strained and distant, they can become irritable and easily irritated, and some show signs of hyperactivity (Clutter, 2010).

Education impact on choosing career path

In school, the teacher is the most important person in a student's life, and he or she has a significant impact on the student in many respects. Daily contact between a student and a teacher results in a lot of knowledge sharing, and students pay attention to what teachers say, which leads to a variety of career opportunities for students. It is now absolutely essential that teachers inform students about different career opportunities. The personal opinion of a teacher about a specific profession may deceive a student, posing a barrier in the selection process (Alloway et al., 2004).

Since high schools serve as a bridge between higher education and the workplace, they play an important role in assisting students in making career decisions. If students have too many career options or haven't decided which one to pursue, school career advice will assist them in choosing study paths and recognizing potential strengths to improve their competition for positions. Self-efficacy, according to Social Cognitive Theory, is the confidence in one's ability to excel at a task. As a result, students are more likely to pursue occupations based on whether or not they have the ability to succeed in them. Schools are critical in training students for their future careers. Schools participate in a number of programs to assist students in coping with the complexities of career decisions, and teachers play an important role in preparing students to effectively progress to the next stage, whether it be for further education or job. There are both public and private schools in Sri Lanka. These schools can have different cultures, which may affect students' career choices. The challenges of offering career counseling differ by school, depending on the characteristics of the students served and the location of schools within a district (Mtemeri, 2017).

Basic needs impact on choosing career path

A child must be well fed, sleep well, feel healthy at home, and have confidence in themselves in order to become successful in school. Being a successful person is usually depending on the financial outcome of the family background is immense.

According to Abraham Maslow, whose theory of Hierarchy of Needs is a well-known theory that focuses on a collection of conditions for performance. He was an American psychologist who created a hierarchy of needs to describe human motivation in 1943.

He explained there were five needs which has to be fulfilled such as: physiological needs, safety needs, love and belonging needs, self- esteem needs, and self-actualization needs, which he arranged into a pyramid (Mcleod, 2020).

Figure 1; Maslow's hierarchy of needs

Maslow ordered these needs in the order in which they must be fulfilled in order for the next to appear. Starting with the most fundamental aspects of basic needs – physiological and safety – and moving up the pyramid to self-actualization, which refers to an individual recognizing their full potential as a human being. Maslow's theory has both proponents and detractors. The main criticism is that his theory is based on philosophy rather than rigorous empirical evidence. The principle, however, continues to serve as a useful reminder that all learners are less likely to succeed if their basic needs are not met. Maslow's hierarchy of needs will assist in focusing on what children need and finding differences, such as offering breakfast to children who arrive at school hungry. In Sri Lanka, how many children have been hungered due to various issues, it leads them to take decisions such as that occur leave the school to start career for fulfill their basic needs. Even they are talented some problems impact them to walk away from academical path (Mcleod, 2020).

Also, most of them are forced drop out from school due to poverty related issues such as lack of supplies of necessary needs (food, clothes, bus fares and etc.), poor family environment and under nourishment etc. Poor students, on the other hand, cannot afford other additional expenses such as contributions for extracurricular activities, bus fares, and other required equipment relating to their studies because they attend schools with insufficient food and other physical and mental health needs. These issues lead them to took wrong decision. Students should have basic physical and mental needs in order to obtain a good education. Even though education is free in Sri Lanka, students can't focus on their studies if they don't have the basic needs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

A student's career choice is undoubtedly the most important decision they will make in their lives. Making these choices can be difficult due to new and changing professions as well as current prestigious preferences. Furthermore, it necessitates a compromise between allowing the student to make an informed decision while still allowing parents and teachers to advise and share their knowledge and experience. Exercising pressure and adopting a dictatorial mentality can demotivate students and reduce their results. To prevent issues, the types of employment that may be important to their desires, abilities, or ambitions should be addressed democratically. Students should choose a profession that is appropriate for their abilities and interests. In this case, the school can assist the student by establishing student counseling centers. As a result, students can quickly determine which career path is best for them. When it comes to choosing a career path, a student's interest can never be overlooked.

CONCLUSION

The paper emphasizes the factors that affect secondary school students' career decisions in Western province, Sri-Lanka. By gathering data from the selected population and other sources, it's analyzed and explained the findings of it. As discussion with population of the study, it can be concluded that parents play an important role which majorly have a negative impact on their children's professional growth. However, children have desires, and parents shouldn't allow them to pursue them, even though they are to become identity.

It also highlights the importance of teachers' support in decision-making. With lack of knowledge and insufficient information about various streams, it's hindered the student's decision-making.

Another factor which impacts career decision making is, children from low-income families attend schools that lack proper resources for a decent education. On the one hand, there are no compelling reasons for children to stay in school longer. On the other hand, such children's socioeconomic circumstances force them to drop out of school and partake in non-academic activities in order to sustain their parents' financial burdens and achievements.

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